

Synthesis and characterization of UO_2^{VI} , ZrO^{IV} and VO^{IV} complexes with Schiff base macrocyclic tetradentate ligand and their derivatives with chloroacetic acid

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Abstract : A series of complexes of the type $[\text{M}(\text{L})(\text{NO}_3)_2].m\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $[\text{VO}(\text{L})(\text{SO}_4)].2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, where L is a Schiff base "2,3,5,6,10,11,13,14-octaaza-1,7,9,15-tetramethyl-1,6,9,14-cyclohexadecatetraene-4,12-dithione" derived from thiocarbohydrazide and acetylacetone have been synthesized. Reaction of these complexes with monochloroacetic acid yielded another series of complexes of the type $[\text{M}(\text{L}')(\text{NO}_3)_2].m\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $[\text{VO}(\text{L}')(\text{SO}_4)].2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, where L' is another Schiff base "4-oxo-2,3,4,5-tetrahydrothiazolo[2,3-b]-2',3',5',6',10',11',13',14'-octaaza-1',7',9',15'-tetramethyl-1',4',6',9',14'-cyclohexadecapentaene-12'-thione" obtained after cyclization with chloroacetic acid, where $\text{M} = \text{UO}_2^{\text{VI}}$ and ZrO^{IV} ; $m = 2$ and 3. All the complexes are characterized on the basis of elemental analysis, thermal analysis, molar conductivity, magnetic moment, electronic, infrared, ^1H NMR and ESR spectral studies. The results indicate that the VO^{IV} ion is penta coordinated yielding paramagnetic complexes where as UO_2^{VI} , ZrO^{IV} ions are hexa coordinated yielding diamagnetic complexes of above stoichiometry.

Keywords : Schiff base, electronic, infrared spectra, ESR spectra, ^1H NMR spectra.

Introduction

Schiff base polyazamacrocyclic complexes have undergone a phenomenal growth during the recent years because of the versatility offered by these complexes in the field of industries, catalysis and in biological systems¹⁻¹¹ etc. Several reports deal with the template synthesis of metal complexes of octaaza macrocyclics. However such complexes involving UO_2^{VI} , ZrO^{IV} and VO^{IV} ions and their reactions with monochloroacetic acid have not been done as yet, which prompted us to study the template synthesis of octaaza macrocyclic complexes of UO_2^{VI} , ZrO^{IV} and VO^{IV} derived by *in situ* condensation of thiocarbohydrazide with acetylacetone and their derivatives with monochloroacetic acid. Such type of investigations were done keeping in view of interesting stereo chemical possibilities, enhanced stabilities and their wide applications in the above mentioned fields. This is a part of our continuing investigation on the coordination chemistry of multidentate ligand containing NOS donors¹².

Results and discussion

The complexes were formulated from the analytical data and molar conductance data support the suggested formulae (Table 1). The complexes are highly coloured

and insoluble in water and common organic solvents such as ethanol, methanol, acetone, CCl_4 , CHCl_3 , benzene and ether but moderately soluble in highly coordinating solvents such as DMF and DMSO. They are highly stable under normal conditions and all of them decompose above 250 °C. The molar conductance data values in DMSO for the complexes indicate them to be non-electrolyte in nature. However, the conductivity value is higher than as expected for non-electrolytes probably due to partial solvolysis of the complexes in DMSO medium¹³.

IR spectra :

As the Schiff base ligand could not be isolated, the spectra of the complexes were compared with spectra of the starting materials and other related compounds. The bands observed in the spectra of metal complexes at ~ 1460 , ~ 1360 , ~ 1050 , ~ 790 cm^{-1} are assigned to thioimide I, II, III, IV bands respectively of TCH skeleton¹⁴. All the above bands appear nearly the same position as found in the free TCH implying non co-ordination of thioimide sulphur or nitrogen atom to the metal ion. The appearance of another band at ~ 1570 cm^{-1} comparatively at lower frequency region than usually free $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ ^{15,16}, lead us to suggest that azomethine nitrogen atom have taken part in complexation as evident from the appearance of bands in

Table 1. Analytical and physical data of the complexes

Sl. no.	Compds.	Colour	Yield (%)	M.p. (°C)	μ_{eff}	Λ_m^a	Found (Calcd.) (%)				
							C	H	N	S	M
1.	[UO ₂ (L)(NO ₃) ₂].3H ₂ O	Cabinet grey	69	>250	Dia	21.27	18.21 (18.27)	3.14 (3.30)	17.72 (17.76)	8.06 (8.12)	30.12 (30.20)
2.	[UO ₂ (L')(NO ₃) ₂].3H ₂ O	Special grey	71.5	>250	Dia	19.35	20.13 (20.29)	3.02 (3.14)	16.84 (16.91)	7.61 (7.73)	28.58 (28.74)
3.	[ZrO(L)(NO ₃) ₂].2H ₂ O	Steel grey	72	>250	Dia	22.68	23.51 (23.72)	3.70 (3.95)	22.95 (23.06)	10.49 (10.54)	14.78 (14.99)
4.	[ZrO(L')(NO ₃) ₂].2H ₂ O	Raw silk	70	>250	Dia	18.93	25.76 (25.96)	3.60 (3.71)	21.45 (21.64)	9.81 (9.89)	14.13 (14.06)
5.	[VO(L)(SO ₄)].2H ₂ O	Truck brown	65	>250	1.80	14.34	28.17 (28.40)	4.42 (4.73)	22.18 (22.09)	12.65 (12.62)	9.91 (10.06)
6.	[VO(L')(SO ₄)].2H ₂ O	Light chocolate	67	>250	1.77	12.50	30.35 (30.71)	4.23 (4.39)	20.41 (20.47)	11.58 (11.70)	9.01 (9.32)

^aΩ⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹.

the region ~490 cm⁻¹ assignable to ν(M-N)¹⁷. In the lower frequency region, the spectra provide a wealth of information on the mode of co-ordination of the ligand with the metal. For the complexes (2), (4) and (6) the band due to ν(C=S) was found to be absent and new bands observed at ~1685 cm⁻¹ due to ν(C=O) and at the region ~800 cm⁻¹ due to ν(C-S) stretching vibration indicating the formation of thiazolidinone ring which was further confirmed by the presence of another band at ~1620 cm⁻¹ for ν(C=N). The uranyl complexes exhibit a strong band at ~945-895 cm⁻¹ and the medium intensity band at ~835-820 cm⁻¹ assignable to ν_{as}(O=U=O) and ν_s(O=U=O) mode respectively¹⁸. The co-ordination of nitrate ions in unidentate manner has been indicated by the appearance of additional band at the region ~1375 cm⁻¹ and ~1045 cm⁻¹ corresponding to the ν₂ and ν₄ modes of the vibration of coordinating nitrate ion under C_{2v} symmetry¹⁹. The zirconyl complexes exhibit one strong band in the region 900-870 cm⁻¹ which can be attributed to the ν(Zr=O) as reported earlier²⁰ indicating the presence of (Zr=O)²⁺ moiety in these complexes. In the oxovanadium polychelates strong bands at ~960 cm⁻¹ are assigned to ν(V=O) modes^{21,22}. However in vanadyl complexes, an additional series of four bands appeared at ~1175, ~1115, ~870, ~650 cm⁻¹ indicating the coordination of sulphate group in unidentate manner through oxygen atom²³. The bands observed at ~3500 cm⁻¹ may be assigned to ν(O-H) of coordinated or lattice water. However all the complexes loss water when heated to ~90 °C indicating the presence of lattice water molecules which has been conformed by thermal analysis.

Thermal analysis :

All these complexes follow the same pattern of thermal decomposition. The complexes remain almost unaffected upto ~50 °C. After this a slight depression upto ~115 °C is observed. The weight loss at this temperature range is equivalent to two water molecules for the complexes (3), (4), (5) and (6) respectively and three water molecules for the complexes (1) and (2), indicating them to be lattice water in conformity with our earlier observations from analytical and IR spectral investigations. Once the lattice water was eliminated, the anhydrous complexes remain stable upto ~350 °C and thereafter the complexes show rapid degradation presumably due to decomposition of organic constituents of the complex molecules as indicated by the steep fall in the percentage weight loss. The decomposition continues upto ~700 °C and reaches to a stable product in each complex as indicated by the consistency in weight in the plateau of the thermogram. This corresponds to the composition of their stable oxides. The decomposition temperature varies for different complexes as shown in Table 2. The thermal stability of the complexes decreases in the order :

In the complexes, weight loss was encountered at ~115 °C to ~115 °C with a broad endothermic peak at the same temperature corresponding to two and three molecules of water of crystallization²⁴.

Table 2. Thermal characteristics of the complexes

Complex	Total wt for T_g (mg)	Temp. range of water loss (°C)	% of water loss Found (Calcd.)	Decomposition temp. (°C)	% wt of residue Found (Calcd.)	Composition of the residue
1	108	55–110	6.79 (6.85)	370–715	35.54 (35.62)	U_3O_8
2	105	55–115	6.47 (6.52)	370–705	33.76 (33.90)	U_3O_8
3	98	50–90	5.85 (5.93)	355–690	20.21 (20.26)	ZrO_2
4	93	45–90	5.51 (5.56)	355–690	18.94 (19.01)	ZrO_2
5	87	40–85	7.04 (7.10)	340–680	35.81 (35.90)	V_2O_5
6	95	45–90	6.53 (6.58)	345–680	33.22 (33.27)	V_2O_5

Electronic spectra and magnetic moment :

The electronic spectra of the UO_2^{VI} complexes are quite similar. The complexes display mainly one weak band at ~460 nm and a highly intense band at ~290 nm, which may be due to $^1\Sigma_g^+ \rightarrow ^3\Pi_U$ transitions and charge transfer transitions respectively²⁵. It may be noted that the band occurring at 372 nm is due to uranyl moiety because of apical oxygen $\rightarrow f^0(U)$ transition²⁶ is being merged with the ligand band due to $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition as evident from broadness and intensity. The electronic spectra of ZrO^{IV} exhibit only one extra highly intensive band in the region 350–380 nm which may be due to charge transfer band besides the ligand bands. However, the electronic spectra could not provide structural details of these complexes. The electronic spectra of VO^{IV} complexes show three bands at ~12350, ~18450 and ~25600 cm^{-1} corresponds to transitions, $d_{xy}(b_2) \rightarrow d_{xz}d_{yz}(e)$, $d_{xy}(b_2) \rightarrow d_{x^2-y^2}(b_1)$ and $d_{xy}(b_2) \rightarrow d_{z^2}(a_1)$ respectively, indicating the complexes to be in distorted octahedral environment under C_{4v} symmetry²⁷. The observed magnetic moments of VO^{IV} polychelates with one unpaired electron lie in the range 1.75–1.80 B.M. and the other complexes are diamagnetic.

¹H NMR spectra :

The ^1H NMR spectra of the diamagnetic complexes are recorded in DMSO- d_6 medium. The complexes show a sharp signal at δ 2.236–2.315 ppm corresponding to imine methyl ($\text{CH}_3\text{-C=N}$; 12H) protons^{28,29}. A singlet is also observed in the region δ 2.248–2.509 ppm, which

may be assigned to methylene ($\text{C-CH}_2\text{-C}$; 4H) protons³⁰. Besides, the signals due to (-NH-N= ; 4H, 2H) protons appear at δ ~6.121–6.225 ppm. An additional peak is also observed in case of the complexes (2) and (4) for CH_2 protons (thiazolidinone ring) at δ ~3.42 ppm (singlet). This suggests the formation of thiazolidinone ring, which is also conformed from the IR spectra of the complexes.

ESR spectra :

The X-band ESR spectra of oxovanadium(IV) complexes are not so resolved at room temperature to exhibit all the eight hyperfine lines as expected for ^{51}V ($I = 7/2$). The ESR spectra of the complexes exhibited anisotropic signals in parallel and perpendicular ^{51}V region. The magnetic and bonding parameters deduced from the spectra are shown in Table 3. This suggests that the unpaired electron to be in d_{xy} orbital localized on the metal, thus excluding any possibility of its direct interactions with the incoming ligands. The covalency parameter α^2 is also calculated. The observed data show that $g_{\perp} > g_{\parallel}$. The representative spectra of the $[\text{VO}(\text{L})(\text{SO}_4)] \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ complex is shown in Fig. 1.

Table 3. ESR spectral data of VO^{IV} complexes

Complexes	g_{\parallel}	g_{\perp}	g_{av}	A_{\parallel}	A_{\perp}	A_{av}	α^2
5	1.96	2.03	2.006	171	69	103	0.48
6	1.97	2.05	2.023	173	72	105.6	0.51

Based on the foregoing observations the following tentative structures have been proposed for the present complexes (Figs. 2 and 3).

Fig. 1. ESR spectra of $[VO(L)(SO_4)].2H_2O$.

Fig. 2. Complexes with L ligand.

Fig. 3. Complexes with L' ligand.

M = UO_2^{VI} , ZrO^{IV} and VO^{IV}
 X = Y = NO_3^- for UO_2^{VI} and ZrO^{IV}
 X = O, Y = SO_4^{2-} for VO^{IV}

Experimental

All the chemicals used of A.R. grade. The solvents were purified before use by standard procedures. Thiocarbohydrazide was synthesized according to literature method of Audrieth *et al.*³¹. As the Schiff base ligand isolation proved futile, all the metal complexes were synthesized *in situ* by taking different amount of metal salts, thiocarbohydrazide and acetylacetone.

Preparation of the complexes of the type $[M(L)(NO_3)_2].mH_2O$, $M = UO_2^{VI}$, ZrO^{IV} and $[VO(L)(SO_4)].2H_2O$:

An ethanolic solution of hydrated metal nitrates/vanadyl sulphate (1 mmol) was added to a hot ethanolic solution of the mixture of thiocarbohydrazide (2 mmol) and acetylacetone (2 mmol). The resulting mixture was refluxed on a water bath for 5–6 h during which a coloured complex was precipitated out in each case. It was filtered off, washed several times with ethanol followed by ether and finally dried *in vacuo* over anhydrous $CaCl_2$.

Preparation of the complexes of the type $[M(L')(NO_3)_2].mH_2O$, $M = UO_2^{VI}$, ZrO^{IV} and $[VO(L')(SO_4)].2H_2O$:

The hot ethanolic suspension of the complexes of the type $[M(L)(NO_3)_2].mH_2O$ or $[VO(L)(SO_4)].2H_2O$, were

treated with chloroacetic acid in 1 : 1 molar ratio. Again, the mixture was refluxed for 4–5 h on a water bath during which the metal complexes of different colour than the precursor complexes were obtained (Table 1). The progress of the reaction was indicated by colour change of the resulting solution. These were filtered off, washed several times with ethanol followed by ether and finally dried *in vacuo* over anhydrous CaCl_2 .

There is possibility of the formation of the mixture consisting reactant complexes and product complexes as the yield is near about 70%. This possibility has been ruled out by carrying out fractional crystallization in DMSO solvent taking in to account their different solubilities.

Physical measurements :

Estimation of uranium, zirconium and vanadium was done by known methods³². Sulphur was estimated as BaSO_4 ³³.

Room temperature magnetic susceptibilities were measured by Gouy method³⁴. The molar conductance measurements were carried out at room temperature with a Toshniwal conductivity Bridge (Model CL-01-06, cell constant 0.5 cm^{-1}) using $1 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$ solution of the complexes in DMSO. Carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen contents of the complexes were estimated by using a MLW-CHN microanalyser. FTIR spectra in KBr pellets were recorded on a Varian FTIR spectrophotometer, Australia. The electronic spectra of the complexes in DMSO were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer* spectrophotometer. Thermogravimetric analysis was done by Netzch-429 thermoanalyser simultaneously recording of TG and DT curves at a rate of $10 \text{ }^\circ\text{C min}^{-1}$ in air. Around 50–100 mg of the sample was used in each case. The ^1H NMR spectra of the complexes were recorded in $\text{DMSO}-d_6$ medium on JEOL GSX-400 model equipment. The ESR spectrum of the complex has only been recorded in solid state on Varian Associate spectrophotometer using 100 KHz, X-band (RT), scan rang $2.0 \times 1 \text{ KG}$ and field set 3200.

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